

Research

One and half Century Long Tree-Climate Relations in Western Nepalese Himalaya

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Abstract: Altitude is a strong determinant factor in the local climate and is an important factor to consider when examining the association between tree and climate relations. Dendroclimatic approach was carried out to examine such relations by extracting the 50 cores of the *Abies spectabilis*. Out of 50 cores, 41 series from 26 trees were well cross dated and samples were analyzed by using ARSTAN program to build the chronology. 155- years long ring width chronology spanning from 1899 to 2017 was developed. The result showed that the growth of *Abies spectabilis* was positively correlated with total precipitation of four months and negatively correlated with eight months in a year. Similarly, the growth of *Abies spectabilis* was negatively correlated with the mean monthly temperature of nine months in a year and positively correlated with the mean monthly temperature of January, August and July only. From the analysis, it was concluded that few months are favorable for the growth of the *Abies Spectabilis* and most of the months were unfavorable. If the moisture availability decreases and drought increase the condition will be more severe in the growth of this plant in the upcoming day.

Keywords: Dendroclimatic approach, Chronology, Moisture, Growth, *Abies spectabilis*

Introduction

Human activities during the industrial period have warmed the climate and could lead to an increase in global average surface temperature of 1.1-6.4 °C by 2100, compared with an increase of around 0.76 °C over the last century (IPCC, 2007). The warming trend has affected ecosystems worldwide (Telwela et al., 2013). High mountain areas are experiencing even greater increases in temperature, especially in the last half-century.

Trees found at the high mountain are exposed to harsh summer and winter climatic conditions. Natural alpine vegetation of High Mountain is climatically highly dedicated ecotone (Körner, 2012) and therefore considered particularly sensitive to altered temperature regimes (Therurillat & Guisan, 2001). Treelines are expected to react strongly to the current and forecasted global warming (Holtmeier & Broll, 2005), either through elevation shifts or through densification of existing forest (MacDonald et al., 1998). Geographical shifts by both plants and animals have widely been recorded in response to climate changes (Walther et al., 2002; Parmesan & Yohe, 2003). These shifts are especially pronounced at the northern and upper margins of species ranges (Hickling et al., 2006) supporting the hypothesis that species will move upward or northward as a response to rising temperatures.

Advancing treeline or a denser forest, tree species shift would have great implications for the global carbon cycle and for the biodiversity of the alpine ecotone. Though a lot of studies have been carried to assess the impacts of climate change into alpine treelines in European and North American Mountains but very limited studies have been carried out in this aspect in the Himalayan (Schickhoff, 2005). In Nepal, very few studies have been carried out to assess the response of the treelines or treelines species to climate change (Suwal et al., 2016). The objective of this study was to access the tree ring and climate relations in the Himalaya of Nepal.

Materials and methods

Study species: Himalayan conifers are highly potential for dendroclimatic studies. Among them *Abies spectabilis* of family Pinaceae and the genus *Abies* has proved its dendroclimatic potential in Himalaya (Gaire et al., 2011). It is distributed up to 4400m from 2400m in Myanmar and eastern Afghanistan (Jacktion, 1994). This species is abundantly found in the Himalayan region of Nepal too. So the study of tree ring of this species and climate relations will help decision-makers for managing the mountain forest ecosystem well in the upcoming days.

Study area: This study was carried out in Lete, Mustang District which is located between two high mountain range of greater Himalaya, Annapurna in the east and Dhaulagiri in the west. Mustang district includes large rain shadow areas with less than 200mm precipitation annually and summer temperature goes up to 26⁰C and winter temperature up to -20⁰C (NTNC,2015). Most of the district is located in the Trans-Himalayan region where the cold desert of climate prevails. The study part is located in the southern part of the district which receives more rainfall than other parts of the district and consists of coniferous species. Lete, altitude ranging from 3200 m to 3300 m was considering for the research site.

Fig.1. A map of study area, Mustang District, Nepal

Field visit and data collection

Data were collected and processed by following dendrochronological methods adopted by Gaire et al., 2011, Kharal et al., 2015 and Aryal et al., 2018 for their research on the conifer of mountain regions of Nepal. Swedish increment borers were used to extract the cores from the trees. A total of 50 cores were extracted from 50 trees of their breast height (1.3m). Extracted cores were instantly kept in the plastic straw pipe with accurate labeling. In addition, the altitude, latitude, and longitude were also recorded.

Laboratory procedure:

Sample preparation: Dendro- lab of Nepal Academy of Science and Technology (NAST) was used for further procedure. A standard dendrochronological procedure was applied for handling and investigating. Collected cores were left for five days for air drying at room temperature. After that, air-dried core was placed in grooved wooden mounts with a cross-section view facing up for 5 more days again. After that, cores were sanded by using sanding machine as well as manually by using various grits of sanding belts and papers from 60 grits to 800 grits until the ring surface became distinctly visible under binocular microscope of LINTAB™.

Sample measurement: Age counting was done with the help of LINTAB and maximum age of the tree was found (1857 to 2012) years which is sufficient to establish tree ring chronology of *Abies spectabilis*. Generally, the chronology is started above 50 years is sufficient. Ring size of each core was measured to the nearest 0.01mm using a LINTAB™ consisting of an attached binocular microscope and a computer program called TSAP-Win (Rinn, 2003).

Cross dating: Cross dating of chronologies was used to remove false rings and identify missing rings so that annual rings are correctly dated. It was done by using software TSAP-Win and the quality of dating was checked by software COFECHA software (Grissino-Mayer, 2001). The tree ring series were repeatedly checked by software COFECHA. The cores which did not get cross dated were eliminated. The aim of cross-dating was also to assign accurate calendar dates to each annual ring of the core. A total of 41 series were chosen for chronology development.

Standardization and Chronology development

The corrected ring width data were standardized using computer software ARSTAN (Cook, 1985). The ring-width series were standardized using conventional detrending methods with appropriate options of a negative exponential, linear or cubic spline curve to each series. Each ring width index series was then pre whitened using autoregressive modeling to remove any autocorrelation effect (Cook, 1987) Finally, 4 different chronologies were developed namely raw chronologies (using cross dated ring-width data), standard chronologies (by detrending cross dated ring-width data), residual chronology (pre whitening the standardized ring-width indices) and the ARSTAN chronology (inbuilt one). Different Chronological statistics like mean sensitivity, standard deviation, auto-correlation, Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), Expressed Population Signal (EPS) was also computed by ARSTAN through which decision on selection between the standard and residual chronology was made for the further analysis. Residual chronology was selected as the fit one for the study.

Tree growth-climate relationship

Instrumental climatic data were collected from nearby metrological stations. There are three metrological stations in Mustang districts. Lete Metrological station is the nearest meteorological station having Precipitation data of 1969 to 2012 but temperature data is limited to 1998 -2012. The correlation between the temperature data of Lete and Jomsom was found highly significant ($P \leq 0.01$) so we use temperature data of Jomsom for tree- climate growth analysis. Pearson correlation analysis was carried out between the residual ring-width index and mean temperature and average monthly precipitation of 30 years, on a monthly basis to analyze tree growth-climate relationships.

Results and Discussions

Tree ring chronologies

Out of 50 cores, 41 series from 26 trees were well cross dated and samples were analyzed by using ARSTAN program. Three different chronologies (raw chronology, standard chronology and residual chronology) from 1857 to 2012 were developed. Gaire et al., 2017 carried out similar research in western Nepalese Himalaya, where they build up a chronology ranging from 1763 to 2013 from 35 cores. The maximum ring width was recorded 2.68 in the year 1997 and minimum ring width was recorded 0.81 in the year 1982. The mean ring width growth of (1852 to 2012) was 1.70. The raw chronology width was compared with its five year moving mean, which showed that growth was seen highest between 1892 to 1902 and growth was lowest in 1872 to 1887. Similarly, in 1942 to 1947 and in 1962 growth was high. On the other hand 2000 to 2005 the growth was slowed.

Table: 1. The Residual chronology statistics of *Abies spectabilis* after standardization

Statistics	Residual Chronology
Chronology Time Span (AD)	155 (1857-2012)
Number of series (Trees)	41 (26)
Mean Sensitivity	0.156
Standard Deviation	0.151
Auto Correlation coefficient	0.102
Common Period	(1941-2012)
Number of series (Trees)	29 (20)
Mean- Correlation among all series	0.283
Mean - correlation within tree	0.508
Mean - correlation between tree	0.279
Effective Chronological Signal	0.355
Signal to noise ratio (SNR)	13.830
Expressed Population Signal (EPS)	0.933

The residual chronology of 155 years long was built from 41 cross dated series from 26 trees. Comparing the chronology of 155 years, the residual chronology has higher mean sensitivity

(0.156), higher standard deviation (0.151), and also auto correlation coefficient (0.102), so it was selected for the tree growth-climate relation. In similar research, Gaire et al., 2017 found that mean sensitivity of residual chronology was 0.152. The threshold limit of EPS was 0.85 (Wigley et al., 1984). The EPS of our finding was 0.933 whereas Gaire et al., 2017 found 0.38. Kharel et al., 2016 develop the chronology range from 1802 to 2013 at an elevation of 3350 to 3400 in the nearest district of our study site. They cored 40 trees in which 30 were cross dated. The mean sensitivity and EPS value was 0.119 and 0.835 respectively.

Climate –Tree growth relationship

Pearson correlation was carried out between the residual chronology and total precipitation (Figure 2a) and mean temperature (Figure 2b) of the Mustang district of the last 30 years on monthly basis using 12 months starting from the previous year (PY) October to current year September. The correlation analysis showed that the tree-ring width was positively correlated with the monthly precipitation of January, April, May as well as November and negatively correlated with the monthly precipitation of February, March, June, July, August, September, October and December. However, highly significant correlation was seen in May ($r=0.385$, $P<0.05$) and highly negative correlation was seen in July ($r= -0.24$, $P<0.05$) (Figure 2a). The tree growth showed a negative correlation with most of the mean monthly temperature except for the current year January, July, and August. The relationship with April is strongly negative ($r= -0.590$, $P<0.05$). Gaire et al., 2014 in Manaslu Conservation Area, where six months are favorable for growth. Similarly, Gaire et al., 2017 carried out the research in Rara national park of western Nepal also found that the growing season of *Abies spectabilis* is more as compared to our finding.

Fig.2. Tree growth response to monthly precipitation & mean monthly temperature.

Conclusion

The study was carried out in Lete, Mustang District, Nepal, which is lying at an altitude of 3300m from the sea level. Despite the difficulty in cross dating, more than one and a half-century-long chronology (1857-2012) was constructed. After analyzing the mean monthly temperature and total precipitation of each month trend of the last 30 years there was an increase in temperature and decreased rainfall. The result showed that the growth of *Abies spectabilis* was positively correlated with total precipitation of April, May, and November and negatively correlated with the rest of the other months of the year. Similarly, the growth of *Abies spectabilis* was negatively correlated with the mean monthly temperature of all months except January, July, and August. This indicates the need of consideration of climate change variability and its impact on growth of *Abies spectabilis* for its effective and sustainable management.

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Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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